

SiC FILAMENT MADE BY RADIO FREQUENCY HEATING CVD

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ABSTRACT

Large diameter SiC filament (0.100mm in diameter) with a tungsten core and carbon rich surface coating has been produced by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) using radio frequency heating. The mechanical properties were studied and the data were analyzed on the basis of the Weibull function. The uniaxial tensile strength distribution contains a sharp maximum with a moderate negative skewness. The average and standard deviation of strengths are 3669.9 and 348.1MPa with a Weibull modulus of 11.9 for a 25mm gauge length and 3584.2 and 403.7MPa with a Weibull modulus of 9.8 for a 50mm gauge length respectively. The results of heat treatment on the filament show that the strength is almost unchanged up to 1000°C .

KEYWORDS: Silicon Carbide; CVD; Radio Frequency Heating.

1. INTRODUCTION

Silicon carbide CVD filament has been considered one of the most attractive reinforcement for MMC and CMC because of their high strength-to-weight and high modulus-to-weight as well as the excellent high temperature stability and oxidation resistance¹⁾. The conventional SiC filament manufacture method is direct current(dc) heating process. The filament is heated to the SiC deposition temperature by dc power applied across mercury contacts in a cylindrical chamber reactor. There is a temperature gradient on the filament due to the variation of the filament diameter that causes the change of the resistivity of the filament²⁾. The mercury contacts could contaminate the filament surface and environment, also damage the human health. The use of radio frequency (r.f.) CVD processing could avoid all the above mentioned disadvantages. The present work deals with the r.f. CVD processing and the strength characterization of large diameter SiC filament.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

SiC filament was produced by deposition of silicon carbide onto a hot tungsten wire substrate about 0.012mm in diameter. As shown in Fig.1, the apparatus includes a r.f. generator. A cable leads the r.f. power into a couple of symmetrical cavity resonator. The resonators create a high dense lineal electrical field between the resonators. W wire substrate can be heated when it passes through the lineal field. By controlling the r.f. power supply and adjusting the resonators, a desirable uniform temperature zone can be obtained along the W substrate, so that a non-contact heating is achieved. As the W wire, heated around 1300°C, continuously passed through a cylindrical chamber reactor which is placed between the resonators, SiC deposition took place. A mixture of methyltrichlorosilane (MTCS) and methylchlorosilane (MDCS) and hydrogen was used in this CVD process. The resulting structure of SiC filament is dependent on the variables such as the composition, flow rate of the vapour mixture and deposition temperature. A little of C_2H_2 was led at the end of the reactor, and a carbon-rich protective layer was obtained on the surface of the SiC filament. The inert gas pressure seals were used to prevent the escape of the mixture reacting gases. The overall diameter of the final filament is commonly 0.100mm.

FIGURE 1. Apparatus for r.f. heating CVD of SiC filament

- 1.-r.f.generator; 2.-r.f.cable; 3.-cavity resonator
- 4.-W wire; 5.-cylindrical chamber reactor;
- 6.-mixture gases inlet; 7.-SiC filament; 8.- C_2H_2 inlet;
- 9.-inert gas inlet; 10.-gas pressure seals.

Tensile testing, used to obtain the room temperature strength histogram, was performed on a UTM-II -20 testing machine at a cross-head speed of 2mm/min. Filament diameter were read with a micrometer to 0.001mm. SEM was used to observe the filament fracture and the surface morphology.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The phase of SiC filament is β -SiC proved by x-ray diffraction. It was also observed a

small amount of W_2C in the filament. Obviously, it is the reaction product between the W core and SiC sheath during the CVD processing. Fig.2 illustrates a high strength filament fractograph, where the filament surface is relatively smooth, and reveals a slight "corn kernel" structure. The fracture in SiC filament initiated predominately at the centre part of the filament. The main defect of the filament was the tumour-like anomaly. It is often caused by stains and defects on the W wire and the impurities from the reacting gases. Fig.3 shows a distinct defect on the interface between the W core and the SiC . This defect nucleated, grew up and finally became a tumour-like anomaly which acted as a filament fracture source. The filament was just broken at the anomaly site.

FIGURE 2. Fractograph of high strength SiC filament

FIGURE 3. Fractograph of SiC filament with anomalies

A study was made on strength distribution. For purpose of comparison of the effect of different specimen gauge lengths on the strength, 25mm and 50mm gauge lengths were

FIGURE 4. Tensile strength distributions for SiC filament at different gauge length

selected. The uniaxial tensile strength distribution of the SiC filament at room temperature shown in Fig.4 contains a sharp maximum with a moderate negative skewness. The average and standard deviation of strengths are 3669.9 and 348.1 MPa and 3584.2 and 403.7MPa for the 50mm gauge length respectively.

The data were also analyzed on the basis of the Weibull function:

$$P_s = \exp \left(-v(\sigma - \sigma_u) / \sigma_0 \right)^m \quad \dots\dots (1)$$

where V is the volume of the filament, σ_u is the stress below which failure never occurs(usually assumed to be zero) and σ_0 is the scale parameter. σ_0 and m are constants for a given material. The Weibull modulus m is a measure of the strength dispersion or the flaw spatial distribution in the filament. Assuming that $\sigma_u = 0$ and the filament diameter is constant along the length L corresponding to the volume V, Equation 1 can be written as:

$$\text{LnLn}(1 / P_s) = m \text{Ln}\sigma + \text{constant} \quad \dots\dots(2)$$

which shows that the plot of $\text{LnLn}(1 / P_s)$ as a function of $\text{Ln}\sigma_0$ must be a straight line, and the slope is the Weibull modulus m^3 .

The curve of $\text{LnLn}(1 / P_s)$ against $\text{Ln}\sigma_0$ are given in Fig.5 for the SiC filaments. The Weibull plots are almost straight line, the Weibull modulus m being 11.9 and 9.8 for the SiC filament with 25 and 50 mm gauge lengths respectively.

FIGURE 5. $\text{LnLn}(1 / P_s)$ against $\text{Ln}\sigma_0$ Weibull plots for SiC filaments with different gauge lengths

Since SiC filament is a kind of fragile materials, large number of flaws or defects distributing throughout the filament control the filament strength, therefore the longer the gauge length, the more the number of flaws and defects, and eventually the lower the filament strength. The results above confirm this point of view.

The effects of heat treatment time and temperature on the filament strength were also investigated. All the treatment were performed on lots of filaments in air. After cooling, the residual tensile strengths were measured at room temperature.

FIGURE 6. Effect of heat treatment temperature on SiC filament strength

Fig.6 shows the effect of heat treatment temperature on the filament strength. Prior to the tensile test, the specimens were kept in temperature of 700, 800, 900, 1000 and 1100°C for 15 min respectively. The filament strength was almost unchanged up to temperature of 1000°C and began to degrade at 1100°C (the strength loss was about 12%). The study of the effect of heat treatment time on the filament strength was also carried out at temperature of 850°C for 30 min, 1h, 2h and up to 72h respectively. It can be seen in Fig.7 that after 30 min and 1h heat treatments, the filament strength losses were

FIGURE 7. Effect of heat treatment time on strength of SiC filament

about 2% and 10%. However, the filament strength was no further degradation for longer

time of heat treatment and after 72h heat treatment, the strength was 5% higher than that of as-received filament.

X-ray diffraction on heat treated filament was performed. The results show that the phase determined was almost the same as compared with that of as-received filament, but different colours from blue to brown could be seen on the surface of filament. All the results strongly suggest that the basic reason for the strength degradation is the filament oxidation during the heat treatments. Since the filament has coated a C-rich protective layer, it acts as a "sacrifice layer" to prevent filament surface oxidation during the heat treatment below 1100°C for 15min in air and the filament strength was unmodified. As the temperature and time of heat treatment increased, the coating was steadily consumed and SiC sheath surface of the filament was oxidated. In this case the filament strength was degraded. However, when the time for heat treatment at 850°C was prolonged, the oxidized layer became thick which prevented oxygen atoms further diffusing and healed the "wound" on the filament surface such as defects and flaws, so that made the filament surface much smooth than before and the filament strength was no longer impaired. But when the temperature of heat treatment was at 1100°C, the oxygen diffusion coefficient became larger, the filament oxidation took place severe and subsequently the filament strength was further degraded.

4. CONCLUSION

Radio frequency heating CVD is an efficient method for preparation of SiC filament. The SiC filament made by this process has excellent mechanical properties and high temperature stability. Flaws and defects which distribute throughout the filament strongly influence the filament strength and the basic reason for filament strength change during heat treatment in air is the filament oxidation.

5. REFERENCES

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